

The effect of competence and motivation on the performance of lecturers in private university

Mijoto Solekan *, Pompong Budi Setiadi and Sri Rahayu

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 14(03), 413–422

Publication history: Received on 14 May 2022; revised on 14 June 2022; accepted on 17 June 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.14.3.0572>

Abstract

Education is a factor that plays an important role in improving human resources who have the abilities and skills needed by every organization. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of competence and motivation on the performance of lecturers at private universities. Data collection through Google Form questionnaire and data analysis techniques with multiple linear regression and path analysis. Data analysis was processed using SPSS version 25 software. The results showed that competence had a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance and motivation had a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance at Nahdlatul Ulama University Sidoarjo. And lecturer performance is more dominantly influenced by the competence variable. This study provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between competence and motivation on performance of lecturers.

Keywords: Competence; Lecturer; Motivation; Performance

1. Introduction

Education is a factor that plays an important role in improving human resources who have the abilities and skills needed by every organization. The crisis of human resources indicates the low quality of education so that every organization demands that existing human resources have the competencies needed to work together in achieving organizational goals. Human resources are assets that have a major influence on the sustainability of an organization, both for-profit and non-profit organizations so that human resources are the spearhead that will determine the direction of an organization as well as in the world of education, human resources in this case are lecturers. determinant in higher education which has a role in transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology, and art for the progress of the nation.

Lecturer performance according to [1] is the ability that has been shown by educators to carry out their duties and responsibilities. Performance is said to be good and has satisfactory results if the goals achieved are in accordance with predetermined standards. The same thing is also needed by universities that already have strong competencies, one of which is a private university in Sidoarjo which has a long-term goal of becoming a university that excels in the development of science, technology, art, and Islamic culture which really requires good performance. of the lecturers in achieving the goals of the university, one of which is by supporting the implementation of good competence and the competence of superior lecturers in their fields so that they can lead to motivation in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in order to be able to carry. Competence and competence on the performance of lecturers with work motivation as an intervening variable at private universities in Sidoarjo.

* Corresponding author: Mijoto Solekan
Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Competence

Competence according to [2] is knowledge, skills and basic values that are reflected in the habit of thinking and acting in other words that competence is a specification of knowledge, skills and attitudes possessed by individuals that are applied in their work based on performance standards. that an organization needs. This shows that competence includes tasks, skills, attitudes and appreciation that must be possessed by human resources to carry out all tasks in their work in accordance with what has been given by the organization. In addition, an understanding of lecturer's abilities refers to the rules of the Ministry of Education. Lecturer competence standards are outlined to fully evolve from the following four key abilities: educational ability, personality, social and Professionalism. These four abilities are built into the lecturer's performance [3].

2.2. Motivation

According to [4], states that social motivation theory is the emergence of attitudes that are influenced by desires in humans. [5] states that the success of educators in improving the national education system cannot be separated from the importance of resources that support teacher performance, motivation, and discipline. Gap studies further focus on improving performance by improving institutions, motivation and culture. The ability and motivation to develop certain traits is desirable.

2.3. Lecturer Performance

Lecturer performance is the ability shown by the lecturer in carrying out his duties or work. According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 Article 1 Paragraph 1 concerning Educators and Lecturers. Educators and Lecturers are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, training, assessing, directing and evaluating students in early childhood education, basic education and secondary education. According to [6] the overall performance comes from the which means of overall performance. Others additionally offers a know-how of overall performance as overall performance, work output, or achievement. Indeed, overall performance has a broader which means, it does now no longer best cowl the work output, however additionally on how the work are processed. Its method that overall performance is the feature of ability, motivation, and opportunity [7]. Thereby, overall performance is decided through elements of ability, motivation, and opportunity. In the alternative level, [8] proposes that lecturer performance is the work output both its first-rate or amount attained through human aid primarily based totally at the attention of lecturer performance and effectiveness in appearing the obligations at the side of the obligations charged on him. Assessment of lecturer performance refers to work first-rate, running rapidity/accuracy, work initiative, work ability, and communication. From the literature review, the conceptual framework of this study is shown below.

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis is as follow:

H1: Competence has an effect on lecturer performance

H2: Motivation has an effect on lecturer performance

3. Method

The type of research used is quantitative research. The population in this study were all permanent lecturers at the NU Sidoarjo University as many as 52 people. In this study using a non-probability sampling technique, namely saturated

sampling is a method of determining the sample if all members of the population are used as samples. The saturated sample is also referred to as a census so that the number of samples taken by the researcher is 52 respondents, which is the entire population.

Researchers used primary data sources which were directly obtained from data collection using questionnaires distributed via Google Form to lecturers at private universities in Sidoarjo. Respondents' answers to the questionnaire were then recorded and processed using SPSS software.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Competence (X1)

The measurement of competency variables uses a questionnaire that has been given to lecturers. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 52 respondents obtained the highest score of 30, the lowest score of 10 with a range of 20, an average of 25.29, a standard deviation of 4.363 and a variance of 19.033. While the quality of competence is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, less agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below:

Table 1 Competence Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	52
N Missing	0
Mean	25.29
Std. Deviation	4.363
Variance	19.033
Range	20
Minimum	10
Maximum	30

Source: processed field data

4.2. Motivation (X2)

The measurement of motivational variables uses a questionnaire that has been given to lecturers. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 52 respondents obtained the highest score of 25, the lowest score of 9 with a range of 16, an average of 22.23, a standard deviation of 3.422 and a variance of 11.710. While the quality of motivation is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, less agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below.

Table 2 Motivation Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	52
N Missing	0
Mean	22.23
Std. Deviation	3.422
Variance	11.710
Range	16
Minimum	9
Maximum	25

Source: processed field data

4.3. Lecturer Performance (Y)

Measuring the lecturer's performance variable using a questionnaire that has been given to the lecturer. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 72 respondents obtained the highest score of 25, the lowest score of 10 with a range of 15, an average of 22.04 standard deviation of 3.378 and a variance of 11,410. While the quality of lecturer performance is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below.

Table 3 Lecturer Performance Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	52
N Missing	0
Mean	22.04
Std. Deviation	3.378
Variance	11.410
Range	15
Minimum	10
Maximum	25

Source: processed field data

4.4. Model Analysis

4.4.1. Validity Test

Whether or not a measuring instrument is valid in a study can be obtained from the results of the validity test. In this competency test (X1) there are 5 statement items, Motivation variable (X2) there are 6 statement items, lecturer performance (Y) there are 5 statement items so that the total question items in this research questionnaire are 16 statement items. The basis for decision making in this validity test if $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$ then it is declared valid and if $r\text{-count} \leq r\text{-table}$ then it is declared invalid. Based on the calculation of $df = N - 2$ with an error rate of 5%, it was obtained $r\text{-table}$ with a value of 0.273. The results of the validity test of each variable can be interpreted in the table below.

Table 4 Competence Validity Test Results Data

		X1.1	X1.2	X1.3	X1.4	X1.5	X1
X1.1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.794**	0.760**	0.744**	0.523**	0.862**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
X1.2	Pearson Correlation	0.794**	1	0.846**	0.813**	0.666**	0.918**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
X1.3	Pearson Correlation	0.760**	0.846**	1	0.881**	0.731**	0.937**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
XX1.4	Pearson Correlation	0.744**	0.813**	0.881**	1	0.810**	0.946**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
X1.5	Pearson Correlation	0.523**	0.666**	0.731**	0.810**	1	0.824**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
X1	Pearson Correlation	0.862**	0.918**	0.937**	0.946**	0.824**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52

Source: processed field data

In the table above. the results of the validity test show that all items in the competence variable statement (X1): numbers X1.1. X1.2. X1.3. X1.4. and X1.5 are declared valid because Pearson correlation value greater than 0.273.

Table 5 Motivation Validity Test Results Data

		X2.1	X2.2	X2.3	X2.4	X2.5	X2.6	X2
X2.1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.870**	0.559**	0.578**	0.502**	0.755**	0.852**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2.2	Pearson Correlation	0.870**	1	0.666**	0.493**	0.432**	0.826**	0.852**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2.3	Pearson Correlation	0.559**	0.666**	1	0.552**	0.383**	0.555**	0.751**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.005	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2.4	Pearson Correlation	0.578**	0.493**	0.552**	1	0.848**	0.590**	0.840**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2.5	Pearson Correlation	0.502**	0.432**	0.383**	0.848**	1	0.596**	0.777**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.001	0.005	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2.6	Pearson Correlation	0.755**	0.826**	0.555**	0.590**	0.596**	1	0.866**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
X2	Pearson Correlation	0.852**	0.852**	0.751**	0.840**	0.777**	0.866**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52	52

Source: processed field data

In the table above. the results of the validity test show that all items in the motivation variable statement (X2): numbers X2.1. X2.2. X2.3, X2.4, X2.5 and X2.6 are declared valid because Pearson correlation value greater than 0.273.

Table 6 Lecturer Performance Validity Test Results Data

		Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5	Y
Y1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.888**	0.733**	0.831**	0.797**	0.932**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
Y2	Pearson Correlation	0.888**	1	0.703**	0.790**	0.872**	0.932**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
Y3	Pearson Correlation	0.733**	0.703**	1	0.757**	0.685**	0.867**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
Y4	Pearson Correlation	0.831**	0.790**	0.757**	1	0.763**	0.908**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
Y5	Pearson Correlation	0.797**	0.872**	0.685**	0.763**	1	0.902**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52
Y	Pearson Correlation	0.932**	0.932**	0.867**	0.908**	0.902**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	52	52	52	52	52	52

Source: processed field data

In the table above, the results of the validity test show that all items in the lecturer performance variable statement (Y): numbers Y1, Y2, Y3, Y4 and Y5 are declared valid because Pearson correlation value greater than 0.273.

4.4.2. Reliability Test

An indicator can be trusted to be used in measuring variables by testing its reliability. The indicator can be declared reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value (α) > 0.6 is obtained and not reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value is $\leq$ 0.6. The results of the data reliability test on the research variables are as follows.

Table 7 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Competence	0.937	5
Motivation	0.902	6
Lecturer Performance	0.943	5

Source: processed field data

From the table above, it is found that all Cronbach's Alpha values are greater than 0.6 so that all variables are declared reliable.

4.4.3. Classic assumption test

Normality Test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov formula is used to determine the normality value of a data on the basis of decision making. ie if the value of sig. > 0.05. stated that the data was normally distributed and if the value of sig. ≤ 0.05 is declared not normally distributed. The results of calculating the normality of the data with SPSS are interpreted in the following table.

Table 8 Normality Test Results

		Unstandardized Residual
N		52
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.44428039
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.130
	Positive	0.115
	Negative	-0.090
Test Statistic		0.090
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.200 ^{c,d}

Source: processed field data

The table above shows the results of data processing where a significance value of 0.200 > 0.05 is obtained. then it is stated that the data has been normally distributed, meaning that the competence and motivation variables on lecturer performance are stated to have normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

The basis used in making decisions on the multicollinearity test is that if the correlation between the independent variables is > 0.10 and VIF < 10 or not more than 10. it means that there is no multicollinearity. The results of the multicollinearity test are interpreted as follows.

Table 9 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.002	1.427		0.702	0.486		
	Competence	0.688	0.086	0.682	8.031	0.000	0.505	1.982
	Motivation	0.225	0.067	0.287	3.377	0.001	0.505	1.982

Source: processed field data

The table above is the result of the multicollinearity test which shows that the two independent variables have a Tolerance value > 0.10, each of which is 0.505 for X1 and 0.505 for X2. Meanwhile, the VIF value obtained by the independent variable < 10, each of which is worth 1.982 for X1 and 1.982 for X2. Referring to the results of the Tolerance and VIF values, it is concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Autocorrelation Test

Autocorrelation test to see whether in the regression model there is a correlation between the nuisance error in period t and the error in the previous period (t-1). One of the autocorrelation tests used is the Durbin-Waston model. The results of the calculation of the autocorrelation test are interpreted as follows:

Table 10 Autocorrelation Test Results

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.907	0.822	0.815	1.473	1.725

Source: processed field data

Based on the table above. the autocorrelation test obtained the Durbin-Watson (d) value is 1.725 with a significance of 5%. the number of samples is 52 (n = 52 and the independent variable is 2 (k = 2). So, the value in the Durbin-Watson table (d) with the value of dL = 1.474 and the value of dU = 1.633. Because the value of d of 1.725 is greater than the upper limit (dU) of 1.6000 and less than 4 - 1.633 (2.366), it is concluded that there is no autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The statistical test used is the Glejser test by regressing the independent variable with the absolute value of the residual. Some alternative solutions if the model violates the assumption of heteroscedasticity is to transform it into logarithmic form. which can only be done if all data are positive. The decision criteria in the Glejser test is if the significance value > 0.05 means that there is no heteroscedasticity. The results of the calculation of the heteroscedasticity test can be interpreted as follows.

Table 11 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.153	0.980		2.198	0.033
	Competence	0.009	0.059	0.030	0.153	0.879
	Motivation	-0.053	0.046	-0.228	-1.157	0.253

Source: processed field data

The results of the Heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser Test method can be seen in the table above. From the output. it is known that the significance value of all independent variables is > 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression model to be analysed.

4.2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 12 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.002	1.427		0.702	0.486
	Competence	0.688	0.086	0.682	8.031	0.000
	Motivation	0.225	0.067	0.287	3.377	0.001

Source: processed field data

From the output obtained. the regression equation model is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 1.002 + 0.688X_1 + 0.225X_2 + e$$

The regression equation model has the following meanings:

- a) The regression coefficients of the two independent variables (competence and motivation) have a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable (Lecturer Performance). This means that every increase in competence and motivation variables will be followed by an increase in lecturer performance variables.
- b) Competence variable has a regression coefficient ($b_1 = 0.688$) which is the largest compared to the regression coefficient of the motivation variable. meaning that lecturer performance is more dominantly influenced by the competence variable.

4.3. Coefficient of Determination of Linear Regression

Table 13 Coefficient of Determination of Linear Regression Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.907	0.822	0.815	1.473

Source: processed field data

From the results of the table above. the value of Adjusted R Square is 0.815. meaning that competence and motivation are able to explain lecturer performance variables of 81.5% while the remaining 18.5% lecturer performance variables are explained by other variables that not investigated in this study.

4.4. Hypothesis Test

To prove the hypothesis in this study. it can be seen from the results of the partial test using the t test. This test aims to determine the significant effect between the independent variables on the dependent variable partially (individually). Basis of decision making:

- a) If the value of $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.
- b) If the value of $t\text{-count} \leq t\text{-table}$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

The value of t-count can be seen from the regression results and for t-table it is obtained from $df=n-k-1= 52-3-1 = 48$ with a significance ($\alpha=0.05$) obtained t-table of 2.0106. The results of hypothesis testing are concluded as follows:

H1: Competence has an effect on lecturer performance. the t-count value is 8.031 and the significance is 0.000. Because the t-count value obtained is greater than 2.0106 so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the hypothesis which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on the lecturer performance is accepted.

H2: Motivation has an effect on lecturer performance. the t-count value is 3.377 and the significance is 0.001. Because the t-count value obtained is greater than 2.0106 so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the hypothesis which states that motivation has a positive and significant effect on the lecturer performance is accepted.

4.5. Managerial Implication

This study provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between competence and Motivation on lecturer performance.

5. Conclusion

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that the two independent variables (competence and motivation) have a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable (lecturer performance). This means that every increase in competence and motivation variables will be followed by an increase in lecturer performance variables and lecturer performance is more dominantly influenced by the competence variable.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Magister Manajemen Mahardhika School of Economics for their support.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

References

- [1] Guci FK. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi, Kompetensi Dosen Dan Kepemimpinan Ketua Program Studi Terhadap Kinerja Dosen Pascasarjana Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara 2020.
- [2] Hakim U. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Personil dengan Motivasi Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Pada Satuan Kodim 0310/KPR). *J Manaj Dan Bisnis Terap* 2020;2:123–32.
- [3] Maklassa D, Nurbaya S. Pengaruh Kompetensi, Motivasi, Sarana dan Prasarana terhadap Kinerja Guru dan Kualitas Pendidikan. *YUME J Manag* 2021;4.
- [4] Najamudin N. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Dosen Melalui Motivasi Dan Lingkungan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Pada Dosen Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan Dan Ilmu Pendidikan (Stkip) Bima) 2018.
- [5] Arifin HM. The Influence of Competence, Motivation, and Organisational Culture to High School Teacher Job Satisfaction and Performance. *Int Educ Stud* 2015;8:38–45.
- [6] Wibowo MK, Ketiga E. Jakarta: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada 2008.
- [7] Robbins PS. *Organization Behavior: Concept. Controv Apl* Prentice Hall Inc, New Jersey 2006.
- [8] Mangkunegara AP. *Evaluasi Kinerja SDM*, Refika Aditama. Bandung Dessler Gary 2012.